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DETERMINATION OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF TERRAZZO SLUDGE IMPACTED SOIL AT ST. PAUL'S CATHOLIC CHURCH AKPO AND ST. JOSEPH CATHOLIC CHURCH AMESI, AGUATA L.G.A, ANAMBRA STATE

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ABSTRACT

Terrazzo sludge generated from a faux material used for flooring in building construction were discharged on the surrounding soils at St. Paul's Catholic church, Akpo and St. Joseph Catholic Church, Amesi in Aguata L.G.A, Anambra State, Nigeria. The aim of the study was to investigate the physicochemical properties of the receiving soils. Soil auger was used to collect the soil samples a depth of 0-10cm from the

edge, 50m, 100m and 500m control of the terrazzo deposit sites during rainy and dry seasons. The physicochemical characteristics of the samples were determined using the process of digestion of heavy metal and using absorption spectrophotometer to analyze soil metal content. Soil pH meter was used to analyze soil pH while oven dry heat was used for moisture content analysis. Conductivity meter was used to determine soil electrical conductivity. Finally, soil organic carbon was analyzed through process of digestion and titration. The heavy metal contents decreased from the deposit sites. Zn was the highest metal recorded both during rainy and dry seasons (Zn new site/rainy-edge 22.1mg/g, 50m 20.3mg/g, 100m 20.11mg/g and 500m control 14.50mg/g and 500m control 14.50mg/g. Conductivity decrease with increase distance new/site rainy edge 3.35, 500m control 1.10. pH 500m control at the new site during rainy season. Moisture content increases away from the dump sites, new site/rainy edge 20.8% and 500m control 30.95%, organic carbon equally increase away from the dump sites. From the result of this study, it was evident that terrazzo sludge affects the properties of the receiving soils. Therefore, there should be proper regulation on the management of terrazzo sludge.

KEYWORDS: Terrazzo sludge, soil, heavy metal, conductivity, moisture content, organic carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Soil can be defined as a composition of organic materials on earth surfaces. Soil is described as an active habitat especially for biological interactions (Fierrer 2017, Bargett and Van Putten 2014). Soil is composed of five major components: mineral matters, water, air, organic matter and living organisms. The quantity of these constituents is not the same in all the soils. Soil is an important part of the earth planet which receives pollutants from a lot of sources but remains an active biological organism Obaro et al., (2016).

Toxic and non-degradable pollutants including heavy metals from cement, deposit into soil (Omoyeni, 2017). Lamare and Sigh (2020) highlighted that these heavy metals undergo chemical processes in the soil, causing soil alkalization and the disruption of the physicochemical properties of plants and soil. Altered parameters in the soil include the level of toxic substances, pH, Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium, Soil texture, Soil organic matter, electric conductivity and soil organic carbon (Jadoon et al. 2022). Also, Silva et al. (2019) indicated that metals are not degradable in nature and therefore get easily accumulated in the soil and vital organs of plants. Furthermore, the spontaneous increase in the population of Nigeria has led to massive urbanization. This has given rise to greater infrastructural development.

Many construction activities using terrazzo as floor materials are common in Nigeria today. The release of terrazzo sludge on soils, results in the reduction of soil permeability and contaminates ground water when deposited along catchment area. This will certainly lead to negative impacts on the soil environment (Wang and Li 2020., Chen and Liu, 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study area**

The study sites were located at St. Paul's Catholic Church Akpo and St. Joseph's Catholic Church Amesi with geographical coordinator of 290379E, 658968N UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator) coordinated respectively in Aguata Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. The sites were designated as old and new sites respectively because of the age of the terrazzo sludge deposit sampled. The terrazzo sludge deposited at the old site is twenty years old while the terrazzo sludge deposited at the new site was just about a month when sampling started.

- **Sample Collection**

Soil samples were taken at different points, starting from the edge of the terrazzo sludge dumps, 50m away, 100m from the terrazzo dumps and 500m away (control) at both old and new sites. Soil sample were collected using auger at the depth of 0 – 10cm. the soil samples were collected in a sterile wide-mouth bottle container with caps and each labelled according to site and distance from where it was collected and then transported to the laboratory for appropriate analysis. The samples were collected in the rainy and dry seasons.

- **Soil Physicochemical Analysis**

The soil physicochemical properties that were determined in this study include: heavy metal content (Zn, Pb, Cr, K, Ca and Fe) pH, moisture, electrical conductivity and total organic matter content.

Heavy Metal Content Analysis

The heavy metal analysis of the samples was carried out according to Majolagbe et al., (2013), 0.5g of samples were weighed into quartz beaker and 10ml of HNO₃ and Hcl was added. They were heated gently on a hot plate until the emitting brown fumes turned white. The mixture was cooled and rinsed with 20mls of deionized water and filter into 50mls volumetric flask. It was analyzed with Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS).

pH Measurement

The pH of the terrazzo sludge contaminated soil samples was measured using pH meter as described by Olaleye and Ayodele (2020). It was determined on 1.1 soil-water mixture composed of 10g soil and 10ml double deionized water. pH meter calibrated with buffers 4,7 and 10.

Moisture Content Analysis

Clean crucibles were dried in air oven for 1hr as described by Lars et al., (2014). The dishes were transferred to a desiccator to cool. Empty dishes were weighed and recorded as (W1). The 5 grams of each solid sample was spread in each dish and weighed accurately as (W2). The dishes and their contents were transferred into the oven set at 105°C to dry the contents for 3hrs. The dishes and the contents were transferred into desiccator using a pair of tongs allowed to cool and weighed as (W3)

Calculations were done thus

% moisture content $W2 - W3 \times 100$

$$\frac{W2}{1}$$

Electrical Conductivity Determination

The electrical conductivity the samples as described by Jackson (1976). Air dried soil of 10g was taken into a beaker and to this, 50ml of water was added. The mixture was stirred with glass rod for 30 minutes. The sample was allowed to settle down and the EC was determined by inserting electrical conductivity meter into the supernatant solution.

Determination of Total Organic Carbon

The Walkey-Black (1934) method was used for the determination. The samples were digested with sulphuric and potassium dichromate (2:1) and allowed to cool. A change occurred in the color of the digest from green to brown when it was titrated with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution which signified end point.

- **Data Analysis**

Date analysis was carried out using the two- way analysis of the variance (ANOVA) means of value determined from each point were evaluated using Bonferroni Correction Post hoc test and significant values were considered at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Generally, the levels of all the heavy metals (Cd, Cr, Pd, Zn, Fe, Ca and P) were higher within the terrazzo sludge polluted areas than the control. The heavy metal contents decreased away from the deposit sites (table 1) Zn was the highest heavy metal recorded both during rainy and dry season and in both new and old site (Zn – new site/rainy-edge 22/mg/g, 50m away. 20.3mg/g, 100m 20.11 mg/g and 500m away control 14.50mg/g), (Zn old site rainy-edge 20.12mg/g, 50m away 20.3mg/g, 100m 15.05mg/g) and 500m away control 13.20 mg/g). Equally, at the new and old sites during dry season, Zn was the highest recorded metal (Zn new site/dry-edge 26. 4mg/g, 50m 23.03 mg/g, 100m 21.22mg/g and 500m away control 17.20mg/g). (Zn old site/dry-edge 23.23 mg/g, 50m 19.80mg/g, 100m 18.10mg/g and 500m away control 18.00 mg/g) Cd level was the least amongst the metal analyzed in both old and new sites in the rainy and dry seasons. (Cd new site/rainy-edge 0.04mg/g, and 500m control 0.02 mg/g). (Cd old/rainy-edge 0.03mg/g, 50m 0.03 mg/g, 100m 0.02 mg/g and 500m away control 0.02mg/g) respectively. While during the dry season it recorded (Cd new site/dry-edge 0.04mg/g, 50m 0.04mg/g, 100 m 0.03mg/g, 500m 0.02mg/g), (Cd old site/dry-edge 0.04mg/g, 100m 0.02mg/g and 500m control 0.02mg/g) respectively.

The pH level of the soil decreases from the edge of the terrazzo sludge dumps from 8.5 to 7.5 in 500m away control in the new site during rainy season and 7.5 at the edge of the dump to 6.5 at 500m away control in dry season (Table 1&2).

Table 1: Composition of heavy metals in soil samples during rainy season

PARAMETER	TSLN	TSN 1	TSN 2	TSN 3	TSN 4	TSLO	TSO 1	TSO 2	TSO 3	TSO 4
Cr mg/g	0.08	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.5	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.02
Pb mg/g	0.36	0.31	0.32	0.24	0.11	0.27	0.24	0.21	0.20	0.18
Zn mg/g	22.51	22.21	20.31	20.11	14.50	20.42	20.12	17.52	15.05	13.20
Fe mg/g	3.32	3.06	2.21	2.01	1.60	2.78	2.36	2.00	1.81	1.72
Ca mg/g	17.02	16.45	12.34	6.49	5.30	14.16	14.13	12.30	8.72	6.02

K mg/g	5.83	5.27	4.12	3.10	2.34	4.51	4.23	3.48	3.03	2.21
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T = Terrazzo

TSLN: Terrazzo Sludge New Site

TSN 1: New site soil sample – edge

TSN 2: New site soil sample – 50m away

TSN 3: New site soil sample – 100m away

TSN 4: New site soil sample – 500m away (Control area)

TSLO: Terrazzo Sludge Old Site

TSO 1: Old site soil sample – edge

TSO 2: Old site soil sample – 50m away

TSO 3: Old site sample – 100m away

TSO 4: Old site sample – 500m away (Control)

Table 2: Composition of heavy metals in soil samples during dry season

PARAMETER	TSLN	TSN 1	TSN 2	TSN 3	TSN 4	TSLO	TSO 1	TSO 2	TSO 3	TSO 4
Cr mg/g	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02
Pb mg/g	0.82	0.72	0.53	0.36	0.33	0.59	0.52	0.32	0.30	0.28
Zn mg/g	29.33	26.46	23.03	21.22	17.20	24.22	23.23	19.80	18.10	18.00
Fe mg/g	5.96	4.10	3.26	2.64	2.20	3.61	3.32	2.34	2.11	2.10
Ca mg/g	9.86	19.24	15.56	11.1	6.42	15.98	15.65	12.80	11.11	11.00
K mg/g	5.38	4.96	4.22	3.44	2.32	4.21	3.43	2.89	2.44	2.36

T = Terrazzo

TSLN: Terrazzo Sludge New Site

TSN 1: New site soil sample – edge

TSN 2: New site soil sample – 50m away

TSN 3: New site soil sample – 100m away

TSN 4: New site soil sample – 500m away (Control area)

TSLO: Terrazzo Sludge Old Site

TSO 1: Old site soil sample – edge

TSO 2: Old site soil sample – 50m away

TSO 3: Old site sample – 100m away

TSO 4: Old site sample – 500m away (Control)

Conductivity decreases with increasing distance away from the dumpsite (table 3&4) the highest soil electrical conductivities were recorded in soils nearest to terrazzo dump sites (New site/rainy-edge 3.18, and old site/rainy edge 3.35) while the least electrical conductivity were recorded in soils at (new site/rainy 500m 1.10 and old site/rainy 500m away control away 1.80), (New site/dry-500m 1.33 and old site/dry – 1.00).

Total organic carbon concentration gradually increases in mg/g as the distance from the dump site increases (table 3 & 4) the concentration varied from 0.84mg/g, 2.6mg/g to 2.81mg/g at sampling new sites edge 50m, 100m and 500m control respectively during the rainy season and 1.21mg/g, 1.61mg/g, 2.76mg/g to 3.69 mg/g at sampling old site edge, 50m, 100m and 500m away control respectively. The moisture content (table 3 & 4) at the edge of the new terrazzo dump soil was 20.5% and 30.95% 500m control but recorded 24;.60% at the edge and 27.45% 500m control at the old dump site during the rainy season.

Table 3: Composition of pH, conductivity moisture content and organic carbon of soil samples for rainy season

PARAMETER	TSLN	TSN 1	TSN 2	TSN 3	TSN 4	TSLO	TSO 1	TSO 2	TSO 3	TSO 4
pH	8.7	8.5	8.2	7.3	7.1	8.2	8.0	7.8	7.6	7.2
Moisture Content %	24.30	20.15	29.65	30.35	30.92	24.60	25.45	27.15	27.60	27.45
Temp °C	34.1	33.2	30.8	29.5	27.5	32.8	32.1	30.2	28.5	28.4
TOC mg/g	0.33	0.84	1.23	2.60	2.81	0.36	1.21	1.61	2.76	3.69
Conductivity	3.32	3.18	2.90	1.90	1.10	3.40	3.25	2.99	2.20	1.80
Cd mg/g	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.4	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02

T = Terrazzo

TSLN: Terrazzo Sludge New Site

TSN 1: New site soil sample – edge

TSN 2: New site soil sample – 50m away

TSN 3: New site soil sample – 100m away

TSN 4: New site soil sample – 500m away (Control area)

TSLO: Terrazzo Sludge Old Site

TSO 1: Old site soil sample – edge

TSO 2: Old site soil sample – 50m away

TSO 3: Old site sample – 100m away

TSO 4: Old site sample – 500m away (Control)

Table 4: Composition of pH, conductivity moisture content and organic carbon of soil samples for dry season

PARAMETER	TSLN	TSN 1	TSN 2	TSN 3	TSN 4	TSLO	TSO 1	TSO 2	TSO 3	TSO 4
pH	7.7	7.5	7.1	6.7	6.6	7.4	7.2	6.7	6.5	6.5
Moisture Content %	22.80	24.00	24.70	25.10	25.50	20.60	22.15	22.80	23.50	23.60
Temp °C	29.7	29.0	28.2	27.9	27.9	30.3	30.0	29.8	27.0	27.0
TOC mg/g	0.70	0.82	1.22	2.10	2.11	0.72	0.97	1.28	2.68	2..60

Conductivity	2.74	2.81	2.20	1.61	1.33	3.10	3.10	3.06	1.28	1.00
Cd mg/g	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02

T = Terrazzo

TSLN: Terrazzo Sludge New Site

TSN 1: New site soil sample – edge

TSN 2: New site soil sample – 50m away

TSN 3: New site soil sample – 100m away

TSN 4: New site soil sample – 500m away (Control area)

TSLO: Terrazzo Sludge Old Site

TSO 1: Old site soil sample – edge

TSO 2: Old site soil sample – 50m away

TSO 3: Old site sample – 100m away

TSO 4: Old site sample – 500m away (Control)

DISCUSSION

The level of heavy metals content decreases as the distance from the terrazzo sludge increases away from the dump site. The result is supported by a similar study carried out by Al-Khashman and Shawabkeh (2006). Equally, the findings agreed with the report of Magolagbe et al. (2013) in their study of trace metal characterization in environmental media and Sowumi et al (2020) in their study of the physicochemical and microbiological characteristics of cement dust polluted site. Similar findings were also reported by other researches Jain and Jain (2006) and Kharmparia et al. (2012): Assessment on the effect of cement dust pollution on soil health, Frederick et al. (2014): The evaluation of selected heavy metals and the effects on impacted soil enzymatic activities in abandoned cement factory, Niger Cement Nkalagu and its environs.

The observed changes in soil's pH is not unconnected with the earlier report of Biden (2010), which stated that changes in soil pH is connected with the content of cement dust in the soil, affecting the soil pH directly. Bayham et al. (2022) and Fabbri et al. (2014) had equally reported that high value of pH of the soil is an indicator of the pollution with cement. The result of pH also decreases with increasing distance from the site and the result agree Ogunyebi and Oludoye (2016). Adak et al., (2001). Bayhan et al (2002) who carried out similar research at Larfage Cement Factory, Sagamu, Ogun state, Nigeria. Uttar cement factory, Pradesh state, India and Askala Cement Plant, Turkey respectively. The results show that there is significant difference pH of control and polluted sites.

The moisture contents of the terrazzo polluted soils were lower than the moisture content of the unpolluted soils as a result of this, the percentage moisture of the soil increases as the move away from the polluted soils to unpolluted soils. This maybe in agreement with the earlier report of Federick et al (2014) which stated that moisture content of cement polluted soil was lower than that of unpolluted soil. The results were attributed to cement dust that coast the soil and consequently prevent penetration of water. Stanley et al., (2014) in their research report agree with result.

Based on the results generally, the level of soil electrical conductivity was found to increase considerably under the effect of terrazzo sludge. This was confirmed by the report of Abdel-Rahman and Ibrahim (2012). Equally, the influence of cement pollution on soil electrical conductivity was confirmed by Amos et al. (2015) the level of conductivity during rainy season was higher in both new site and old site, when compared to the results during the dry season in both new and old sites.

The amount of soil organic carbon at the terrazzo dump site was found to be increasing with an increasing distance away from the dump sites. Similar findings were reported by Cris-customized rainfall information from Indian meteorological department (2023), Liwat and Katiyar (2015), Abdel and Ibrahim (2012). Magray study on the impact of cement dust on the selected vegetable crops, equally found that total organic carbon content in soil tend to increase with increasing distance from the cement factory. Results of the study made by Eugene and Singh (2020) on the effect of cement on soil physicochemical properties around cement plants were in agreement with these findings.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, it was concluded that terrazzo sludge affects the physicochemical property of the receiving soil. This result shows that heavy metal, pH and electrical conductivity of the affected areas were high while the moisture and organic carbon content of the affected areas were low.

In view of this results, there should be proper regulations on management of terrazzo waste to reduce its effects on the properties of the receiving soils.

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